

Estimation of lamotrigine in pharmaceutical preparations

K. Sharma^a and S. C. Lahiri^{b*}

^aVivekananda Mahavidyalaya, Haripal-712 403, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

E-mail : ksharma71@yahoo.co.in

^bCentral Forensic Science Laboratory, 30, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India

E-mail : suijtelahiri@yahoo.com Fax : 91-33-22849442

Manuscript received 16 June 2011, accepted 30 December 2011

Abstract : Lamotrigine (LTG) is an important anticonvulsant drug used in the treatment of epilepsy and all kinds of seizures.

Due to its importance, the assay of LTG in commercial tablets attracted much attention. The chloranillic acid in acetonitrile was found to be most suitable for the assay of LTG in different pharmaceutical dosage forms in a simple way, which is described in this article. The CT complex between *p*-chloranilic acid and lamotrigine at 521 nm was used to determine accurately the concentration of lamotrigine in tablets.

Keywords : Lamotrigine, lamez, Lamitor-DT, UV-Visible spectrophotometry, estimation, LOD, LOQ.

Introduction

Lamotrigine (LTG) is an important anticonvulsant drug used in the treatment of epilepsy and all kinds of seizures (consisting of different types of seizures including severe seizures like Lennex-Gastaut syndrome [a disorder of childhood characteristic by multiple seizure types], mental retardation and refractoriness to anti-seizure medication), bipolar disorder or mood stabilizer¹. Due to its importance, the assay of LTG in commercial tablets attracted much attention. Identification of LTG and estimation using TLC and spectrophotometric methods are known. Suitable sensitive methods for the identification and quantification of LTG in pharmaceutical dosage forms and urine samples etc. are needed. Recently, Youseef and Taha² developed spectrophotometric, TLC and HPLC methods for the determination of lamotrigine in presence of impurities. They used CT complex formation between *p*-chloranilic acid and lamotrigine at 519 nm to determine accurately the concentration of lamotrigine in tablets. Alizadeh *et al.*³ suggested a method of spectrophotometric estimation of LTG in pharmaceutical dosage forms based on charge-transfer complexes between LTG with acceptors like bromocresol green (BCG), bromocresol purple (BCP) and chlorophenol red (CPR) in chloroform solutions. Vinay *et al.*⁴ and Rajendrapuri *et al.*⁵ also gave

simple methods of determining lamotrigine based on drug-dye (1 : 1) ion-pair formation between LTG and BCG at pH 5.02 ± 0.01 and LTG + BCP at pH 2.40 ± 0.01. The complexes were extracted in dichloromethane, followed by spectroscopic measurements at 410 nm to estimate LTG accurately. They also used other methods to estimate LTG.

In course of our studies on charge-transfer and H-bonding complexes of LTG with acceptors, it was observed that LTG formed beautifully colored charge-transfer complexes with acceptors like *o*-chloranil (*o*-ClN), chloranillic acid (CIA) and 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyanobenzoquinone (DDQ) of which the chloranillic acid in acetonitrile was found to be most suitable for the assay of LTG in different pharmaceutical dosage forms in a simple way, which is described in this article. The results of our investigation are described in this article.

Experimental

Purified lamotrigine (99.8% purity) obtained from Dr. (Ms.) N. Saha, Central Drug Laboratory, Kolkata was used as such. *o*-Chloranil (Fluka), chloranillic acid and DDQ (Aldrich, Sigma, R & D grade) (98% purity) were used as such. Acetonitrile (ACN) and other solvents used were of HPLC grade from E. Merck. Shimadzu Double

Beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Model UV 2550) fitted with Peltier controlled thermo-regulated cell compartment was used for spectrophotometric measurements. The analysis of the spectrophotometric data was made with UV-probe software. LTG is insoluble in many solvents including water. LTG and particularly acceptors interact with many solvents and the optical density values of the complexes were found to change with time. But no interaction was observed for the acceptors (*o*-CIN, CIA and DDQ) in acetonitrile and their complexes with LTG were found to be fairly stable in ACN which made ACN to be desired solvent for study. Out of these beautifully colored complexes the complex with LTG + CIA with λ_{max} , 521.0 nm was utilized for the estimation of LTG. At 521.0 nm, the 1 : 1 complex of LTG + CIA absorb strongly, LTG do not absorb but CIA has very weak absorption.

Assay of LTG in pharmaceutical tablets :

(a) Preparation of experimental solutions :

In India, lamotrigine is sold and readily available under the trade name Lamez-25 (Intas Pharmaceutical Ltd., Ahmedabad, India) containing 0.1106 g/tablet and Lamitor-DT-25 (Torrent Pharmaceutical Ltd., Solan, Himachal Pradesh, India) containing 0.0975 g/tablet. There are other brands of LTG as well. 5 tablets of each the drug Lamez-25 and Lamitor-DT-25 were powdered separately. Powdered 0.0523 g Lamez and 0.0550 g Lamitor were dissolved in acetonitrile separately in two beakers. LTG was completely soluble in acetonitrile leaving insoluble ingredients or incipient as such. The contents of

each beaker filtered separately in 100 ml volumetric flasks. The residuals were washed repeatedly with acetonitrile, taking the filtrate in the volumetric flasks respectively and the filtrate were made upto the mark (100 ml).

(b) Preparation of standard solutions of LTG and chloranilic acid in ACN :

Requisite amount of LTG (0.0256 g) and chloranilic acid (0.0209 g) were dissolved in acetonitrile and made upto the mark (100 ml) with ACN in 100 ml volumetric flasks to make 1.0015×10^{-3} (M) solutions each of LTG and CIN.

(c) For the assay of LTG in tablets, four different sets of solutions were prepared :

(A) 4 ml Chloranilic acid solution + x ml standard LTG solutions were made upto 10 ml with ACN.

(where, x = 1.0 ml to 4.0 ml at an interval of 0.5 ml)

(B) 4 ml Chloranilic acid solution + y ml Lamez solutions were made upto 10 ml with ACN.

(where, y = 3.0 ml to 5.0 ml at an interval of 0.5 ml)

(C) 4 ml Chloranilic acid solution + z ml Lamitor solutions were made upto 10 ml with ACN.

(where, z = 3.0 ml to 5.0 ml at an interval of 0.5 ml)

(D) 4 ml Chloranilic acid solution was made upto 10 ml in ACN. This was used as a blank solution for all the experiments.

Optical density measurements of the standard solutions and the experimental solutions were made (Figs. 1-4)

Fig. 1. UV-Visible spectrum of Lamotrigine.

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectrum of Chloranilic acid.

Fig. 3. UV-Visible spectrum of CT complex of Lamez + CIA.

against 4 ml chloranilic acid in acetonitrile (as blank). A linear calibration curve (Fig. 5) was obtained ($y = 0.0044x + 0.0093$, $R^2 = 0.9948$) when optical densities of the solutions were plotted against concentrations of LTG. The concentrations of LTG in Lamez or Lamitor in the experimental solutions B and C were obtained from the calibration curve and percentage recovery was calculated.

The results are the averages of duplicate set of readings and each reading was taken three times for any particular solution.

Results and discussion

The results given in Tables 1 and 2 show the percentage recovery of LTG from the tablets are nearly 96% and

Fig. 4. UV-Visible spectrum of CT complex of Lamitor + CIA.

Fig. 5. Standard concentrations of LTG in LTG + CIA CT complex vs absorbance curve.

Table 1. Concentrations of LTG in Lamez-25 in the experimental solutions, absorptions and percentage recovery

Sl. no.	Conc. of LTG in Lamez-25 (taken) (µg/ml)	Absorbance of Lamez +CIA CT complex	Conc. of LTG in Lamez-25 (exp. obtained) (µg/ml)	% of recovery	Average % of recovery
1.	35.47	0.15927	34.1	96.1	96.8
2.	41.38	0.18623	40.2	97.2	
3.	47.29	0.21221	46.1	97.5	
4.	53.2	0.23585	51.5	96.8	
5.	59.11	0.25948	56.9	96.2	

appear to be reasonable. The limits of detection (LOD = $3.3S/b$) and limits of quantification (LOQ = $10S/b$) are given in Table 3 [S is the standard deviation of blank

Table 2. Concentrations of LTG in Lamitor-DT-25 in the experimental solutions, absorptions and percentage recovery

Sl. no.	Conc. of LTG in Lamitor-DT-25 (taken) (µg/ml)	Absorbance of Lamitor-DT-25 +CIA CT complex	Conc. of LTG in Lamitor-DT-25 (taken) (µg/ml)	% of recovery	Average % of recovery
1.	30.77	0.13925	29.53	95.98	96.3
2.	35.89	0.16221	34.75	96.83	
3.	41.03	0.18413	39.73	96.84	
4.	46.15	0.20634	44.78	97.03	
5.	51.30	0.22363	48.71	94.99	

Table 3. The analytical performance of UV-Visible spectrophotometry for the estimation of phenolphthalein

Method	Limit of detection (µg/ml)	Limit of quantification (µg/ml)
UV-Vis spectrophotometry	0.008	0.026

absorbance values and b is the slope of the calibration plot]. Charge-transfer complexes are generally used for the identification of drugs and quantification by methods like spectrophotometry, HPTLC etc. But quantification of drugs (donors) is possible if the drug is completely converted into complex by addition of excess of acceptors. The complex must have sharp absorption at a particular wavelength whereas the donor and acceptors should have no absorption in the region under study and the

complex should obey Beer-Lambert's law at low concentration region. These conditions were fulfilled in case of ferriin, ferriidii complexes⁶ and TNT complexes with amines⁷. However, in most cases of charge-transfer complexes, complete complex formation is not a reality. Considerable uncertainty exists in ϵ (the extinction coefficient) values of the complexes determined using extrapolation method. There is considerable uncertainty in the estimation of drugs by extrapolation method taking ϵ -value of the complex using Benesi-Hildebrand or similar methods. Ion-pair formation between drugs and dyes at different pHs like 5.02 ± 0.01 or 2.40 ± 0.01 were not theoretically or experimentally correct if we considered the pK_{In} values i.e. 4.8 for BCG, 6.3 for BCP and $pK_{LTG} = 5.7$ i.e. under the conditions of the experiment, the drugs or indicators were not totally ionic or basic i.e. complete conversion of the acceptors and donors into complex is not possible and the compositions of the complex are expected to vary. Moreover, the workers determined the association constants of the drug-dye complexes i.e. drug was not completely converted into complex.

We also utilized the complex formation of LTG and CIA in the visible region to estimate the quantity of the drug present in the tablets. It had been found that weights of the tablets were different but the amount of the drug was almost the same as claimed by the manufacturer though slight differences existed. It is to be noted that the composition of the complex was immaterial as the plots of absorbance or o.d's of the experimental and standard solutions were made against the concentrations of LTG both for the standard solutions and the experimental solutions. It is true for all the experiments and if the conditions are similar, any method will give the expected results. The complexes, however, must be stable. In this case, LTG

taken in a non-interacting solvent, can be accurately estimated spectrophotometrically by measuring o.d of solutions at 305 nm. HPLC and LC-MS/MS can be utilized for better results in presence of impurities.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Dr. C. N. Bhattacharyya, Director, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, Kolkata, for helping them in all possible ways to carry out the work and allowing laboratory facilities. One of the author Mrs. Kakali Sharma thanks UGC, Government of India for awarding Teacher Fellowship to her under the College Faculty Improvement Programme.

References

1. (a) J. O. Mc Namara, in "Goodman & Gilman's The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 11th ed., eds. L. L. Brunton, J. S. Lazo and K. L. Parker, McGraw Hill, Medical Publishing Division, 2006, pp. 501-526; (b) C. G. Wermuth, in "The Practice of Medicinal Chemistry", 2nd ed., ed. C. G. Wermuth, Elsevier, 2003, p. 25.
2. N. F. Youssef and E. A. Taha, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2007, **55**, 541.
3. N. Alizadeh, R. Khakinahad and A. Jabbari, *Pharm. Die*, 2008, **63**, 791.
4. K. B. Vinay and H. D. Revanasiddappa, *J. Food Drug Anal.*, 2009, **17**, 424.
5. N. Rajendraprasad, K. Basavaiah and K. B. Vinay, *Eclat. Quim.*, 2010, **35**(1).
6. (a) S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1964, **41**, 173; (b) S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1964, **43**, 282; (c) S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1967, **55**, 6; (d) S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 2487; (e) D. K. Hazra and S. C. Lahiri, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **79**, 335.
7. S. P. Sharma and S. C. Lahiri, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2008, **70**, 144.

